

Multisystem Involvement in Postpartum Takayasu Arteritis: Vascular Complications and Dilated Cardiomyopathy. A Case Report and Review of Literature

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Abstract:

Background: Takayasu arteritis is a rare large vessel vasculitis that can present unique challenges, particularly in young post-partum women.

Objective: To report a rare case of a young post-partum patient diagnosed with Takayasu arteritis, complicated by heart failure highlighting notable vascular abnormalities.

Case presentation: A 21-year-old female was admitted with symptoms of acute decompensated heart failure, initially attributed to peripartum cardiomyopathy. During hospitalization, she developed severe abdominal pain and cardiovascular instability with an absent left radial pulse. Further evaluation led to a diagnosis of Takayasu arteritis with multi-vessel involvement. Treatment with standard heart failure therapy and high-dose corticosteroids with immune suppressive therapy resulted in improved cardiac function.

Conclusion: This case underscores the complexity of diagnosing and managing a 21-year-old female with concurrent Takayasu arteritis and acute decompensated heart failure. It highlights the critical need for early identification and comprehensive evaluation of cardiovascular conditions in post-partum patients, as timely intervention can lead to significant improvements in outcomes. The successful treatment and positive response to therapy in this case reinforce the importance of adhering to guideline-directed medical therapy.

Keywords: Takayasu Arteritis, peripartum cardiomyopathy, vasculitis, heart failure, Addis Ababa

Declaration

Ethical approval: Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional review board of St. Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College and is available to the editors upon request

Consent for publication: Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal upon request.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests

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Abbreviation

- ANA- antinuclear anti body
- ANC- antenatal care
- BP- blood pressure
- CRP- c-reactive protein
- CT- computed tomography
- EF- ejection fraction
- ESR- erythrocyte sedimentation rate
- GDMT- guideline directed medical therapy
- IVC- inferior vena cava
- PND- paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea
- PPCM- peri partum dilated cardiomyopathy
- RCVS- reversible cerebral vasoconstriction syndrome
- TAK- takayasu arteritis
- TB- tuberculosis
- TTE- trans thoracic echocardiogram

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